

the amide I band, is always shifted to a lower frequency by 15-40 cm^{-1} in the metal complexes, indicating the participation of the C=O group in coordination. Also, a positive shift of 20-65 cm^{-1} of the N-O stretch (1015 cm^{-1} in the ligand) in the chelated species is diagnostic of the oxime nitrogen coordination⁶. The C=N (azomethine) stretching frequency at 1590 cm^{-1} in the free ligand is found to be shifted to a lower frequency by 5-15 cm^{-1} in the complexes, suggesting its involvement in coordination. Regarding the complexes of the enol form of the ligand, which do not contain any water molecule, no identifiable absorption band in the region 3600-3200 cm^{-1} are present pointing to the absence of the -OH as well as the -NH groups. The strong amide I band at 1640 cm^{-1} is absent in all these complexes indicating the enolisation of the keto group and its participation in complexation in the enolate form. The N-O stretching frequency in all the complexes of the enol form has been observed at a higher frequency than is present in the original ligand. Cryomagnetic study of the Cu(II) complex of the enol form of the ligand is in progress and will be reported in near future.

References

1. W. E. HATFIELD and R. WHYMAN, "Transition Metal Chemistry", 1969, 5, 47.
2. D. J. HODGSON, "Progress in Inorganic Chemistry", 1975, 19, 1.
3. J. A. BERTRAND and P. G. ELLER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, 9, 13, 928.
4. B. N. FIGGIS and C. M. HARRIES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 855.
5. L. J. BELLAMY, 'The Infrared Spectrum of Complex Molecules', Chapman and Hall, London, 1975.
6. K. BURGER, I. RUFF and F. RUFF, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1965, 27, 179.

Nickel(II) Mixed Chelates Containing Two Bidentate Monobasic Hydroxyaldehyde (or Ketone) and a Bidentate (NN) Heterocycle

R. L. DUTTA and ANJANA BHATTACHARYA

Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan,
Burdwan-713 104, West Bengal

Manuscript received 6 November 1979,
accepted 20 December 1979

WE have recently described^{1,2} a series of pseudooctahedral nickel(II) mixed chelates containing a dibasic tridentate (ONO) Schiff base like salicylideneamino acid, one dipyrindyl (or *o*-phenanthroline) and a molecule of water. The most useful method of synthesis of these mixed chelates involved a template reaction on *bis*(salicylaldehydato) dipyrindyl nickel(II) and related complexes by the desired amino acids. Only a passing reference³ to *bis*(3-nitrosalicylaldehydato) dipyrindyl nickel(II) is

available in the literature. We report in this note several nickel(II) mixed chelates containing two hydroxy aldehydes (or ketones) and one dipyrindyl (or *o*-phenanthroline) with a fond hope that these mixed chelates may serve as useful precursors in forcing novel template reactions with chosen amines or amino acids. The following abbreviations have been used :

SalH = salicylaldehyde ; 5-Cl-salH = 5-chlorosalicylaldehyde ; 5, 6-benzosalH = 5, 6-benzosalicylaldehyde ; hacH = 2-hydroxyacetophenone ; dipy = dipyrindyl and *o*-phen = *o*-phenanthroline.

Experimental

Bis(salicylaldehydato) diaquo nickel(II)⁴ and other similar complexes were synthesised by published procedures.

Bis(salicylaldehydato) dipyrindyl/*o*-phenanthroline nickel(II) :

Bis(salicylaldehydato) diaquo nickel(II) (0.002 mol) in alcohol (50 ml) was allowed to reflux with the heterocyclic base (0.002 mol) for fifteen minutes. The green solution was filtered hot, concentrated to 10 ml, scratched and cooled in a refrigerator overnight. The green crystals were collected, dissolved in minimum volume of refluxing chloroform, filtered and cooled in ice. Finally the crystals were dried in air.

Bis(5-chlorosalicylaldehydato) dipyrindyl/*o*-phenanthroline nickel(II) :

The chloroform solution obtained as above was concentrated to 2-3 ml. To this solution 5 ml alcohol was added with stirring and then left in a refrigerator overnight. Yellowish green crystals were collected and dried in air.

The remaining compounds were obtained by following the above procedures with or without some slight variation in the volume of solvent etc. The characterisation data are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The magnetic moments (Table 2) lie in the range 3.14-3.24 B.M. being consistent with pseudooctahedral stereochemistry⁵. Their non-electrolytic nature⁶ in methanol rules out any alternative ionic formulation such as $[\text{Ni}(\text{sal})(\text{dipy})_2]^+ [\text{Ni}(\text{sal})_3]^-$. Nujol mull spectrum of $[\text{Ni}(\text{dipy})(\text{sal})_2]$ reveals two bands at ~ 10.2 kK (ν_1) and ~ 16.7 kK (ν_2) (Table 2). The absorption peaks are somewhat broad, thus indicating considerable distortion from octahedral geometry⁷. ν_1 and ν_2 are assigned as the transitions : ${}^3A_{2g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(\text{F})$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(\text{F})$ in O_h symmetry. ν_3 transitions could not be located with

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF NICKEL(II) MIXED CHELATES (DRIED AT 120°C)

Chelates	Colour	Ni (%)		N(%)	
		Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
[Ni(dipy)(sal) ₂]	Green	12.6	12.8	6.2	6.1
[Ni(o-phen)(sal) ₂]	Yellowish green	12.3	12.2	5.4	5.8
[Ni(dipy)(5-Cl-sal) ₂]	Green	10.9	11.2	5.1	5.3
[Ni(o-phen)(5-Cl-sal) ₂]	Yellowish green	10.8	10.7	5.1	5.1
[Ni(dipy)(5,6-benzosal) ₂]	Light green	10.3	10.5	5.1	5.0
[Ni(o-phen)(5,6-benzosal) ₂]	Brownish green	9.9	10.1	4.7	4.8
[Ni(dipy)(hac) ₂]	Green	11.9	12.1	5.5	5.8
[Ni(o-phen)(hac) ₂]	Yellowish green	11.6	11.5	5.3	5.5

Some of the air dried hydrated compounds were analysed for carbon, hydrogen (at C.D.R.I., Lucknow) and lattice water with satisfactory results.

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC MOMENT, CONDUCTIVITY AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF NICKEL(II) MIXED CHELATES

Chelates	Magnetic moment (B.M.)	Conductivity in methanol (ohms ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹)	$\nu_1(\epsilon)=10Dq$, kK	$\nu_2(\epsilon)$, kK	ν_2/ν_1
[Ni(dipy)(sal) ₂]H ₂ O	3.19	2	10.20 ^a	16.7 ^a	1.64
[Ni(o-phen)(sal) ₂]1.5H ₂ O	3.20	1	10.21(12.9) ^b	16.66(24.2) ^b	1.63
[Ni(dipy)(5-Cl-sal) ₂]H ₂ O	3.19	1	10.21(9.3) ^b	16.66(13.9) ^b	1.63
[Ni(o-phen)(5-Cl-sal) ₂]1.5H ₂ O	3.24	1	10.21(11.0) ^b	16.66(20.8) ^b	1.63
[Ni(dipy)(5,6-benzosal) ₂]	3.17	2	10.60 ^a	17.20 ^a	1.23
[Ni(dipy)(hac) ₂]1.5H ₂ O	3.20	1	—	16.94(7.2) ^c	—

a=nujol mull ; b=chloroform ; c=ethanol.

certainty because of the high absorption of the heterocyclic donors. The spin-forbidden transition ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ could be detected in solution spectra in the region 11.3-13.2 kK (ϵ 3.0-8.5). The $\nu_2 : \nu_1$ ratios of the mixed chelates are around 1.62 indicating the pseudo-octahedral nature of the chelates⁸. The $10 Dq (= \nu_1)$ values are consistent with the $10 Dq$ values of other [NiN₂O₄] chromophores (e.g. [Ni(tmen)(tfa)₂]⁹ : $10 Dq=9.8$ kK ; tmen=N, N, N¹, N²-tetramethyl ethylenediamine and tfa=trifluoroacetylacetate ion).

The infrared spectrum of [Ni(dipy)(sal)₂] registers band at 1613 ($\nu_{C=O}$)¹⁰, 1580 cm⁻¹ (ν_{C-O})¹¹ and 740 cm⁻¹ (ν_{dipy}). The $\nu_{C=O}$ band of [Ni(H₂O)₂-(sal)₂] appears at 1640 cm⁻¹ and a typical dipyriddy band of [Ni(OH₂)Cl(dipy)₂]Cl.2H₂O shows up at 740 cm⁻¹. Thus we are convinced that in these mixed chelates we have both the hydroxyaldehyde and the heterocyclic donors coordinated to nickel(II).

Acknowledgement

We thank CSIR for financial assistance.

References

1. R. L. DUTTA and A. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 668.
2. R. L. DUTTA and A. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.* (in press).
3. Y. MUTO, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1960, **33**, 604.

4. A. D. DAMODARAN, F. M. ICHAPORIA and G. S. RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **45**, 690.
5. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, *Advanced Inorganic Chemistry*, 3rd Edition, Interscience, New York (1972).
6. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Revs.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
7. J. R. MILLER, *Advances in Inorganic and Radiochemistry*, (Ed.) H. J. EMERUS and A. G. SHARPE, Academic Press, 1962, Vol. 4, p. 148.
8. L. SACCONI, 'Transition Metal Chemistry', (Ed.) R. L. CARLIN, Mer el Dekker, New York, 1968, Vol. 4, p. 214.
9. Y. FUKUDA and K. SONE, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 455.
10. R. H. BALUNDGI and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **12**, 981.
11. A. R. KATRITZKY, A. R. HANDS and R. A. JONES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3165.

Mixed Ligand Complexes. Part IX.

Methioninato bis(biguanide) Cobalt(III) Salts

R. L. DUTTA and ANJANA BHATTACHARYA

Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan,
Burdwan-713 104

Manuscript received 6 November 1979, accepted 20 December 1979

MMETHIONINE(1) is a flexidentate ligand being capable of chelating as a tridentate (SNO) and bidentate (SN) and (NO) donors. Preparation and properties of the mixed chelate [Co(meth)(BigH)₂]²⁺ (meth H=methionine) were undertaken to ascertain the donor sites. Attempts to synthesise